

Examining the Components of Positive Psychology in the Poetry of Haidari Wujudi Based on Martin Seligman's Theory

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Abstract: Background and Purpose: Positive psychology is one of the most modern branches of psychological science. It focuses on unique human strengths, capacities, and values with the aim of enhancing well-being and improving life quality. By identifying and classifying human virtues and strengths, and uncovering hidden dimensions of human existence, this field helps individuals harness internal and external forces. This branch of psychology encompasses concepts such as wisdom, love, compassion, altruism, happiness, resilience, optimism, and hope, and aims to reinforce and promote them. Dari Persian literature has historically embraced and promoted such concepts. Haidari Wujudi is one of the contemporary Dari Persian poets whose work consistently addresses themes aligned with positive psychology. This study aims to investigate the components of positive psychology in the poetry of Haidari Wujudi, examining the poet's views through the lens of Martin Seligman's theories.

Research Method: Based on its purpose, this study is fundamental–theoretical, exploring the nature of phenomena. Methodologically, it is descriptive–analytical, and data collection was conducted through library research.

Findings: The analysis of Wujudi's poetry in light of positive psychology components revealed several themes that align closely with the theoretical framework. The findings indicate a strong correlation between the core concepts of Seligman's positive psychology and the themes found in Haidari Wujudi's poetry.

Conclusion: The six core virtues of Seligman's positive psychology—wisdom, courage, humanity, justice, temperance, and transcendence—are evident throughout Wujudi's poetry. Under the virtue of wisdom, traits such as a thirst for knowledge, curiosity, critical thinking, innovation, social intelligence, and perspective are observed. Under courage, attributes like persistence, honesty, tolerance, and resilience appear. Under humanity, values such as human dignity, compassion, altruism, love, and affection are prominent. Under justice, themes of citizenship, teamwork, fairness, equality, and leadership are visible. Under temperance, qualities like humility, self-control, and thoughtful behavior emerge. Finally, under transcendence, we find appreciation of beauty and excellence, spirituality, mercy and generosity, purposefulness,

hope, optimism, joy, and loyalty. Wujudi has conveyed these values and traits effectively through his poetic expression.

Keywords: *Haidari Wujudi; Wujudi's Poetry Collection; Positive Psychology; Martin Seligman; Positive Thinking*

Introduction

Psychology is a science that, through defining and describing the surrounding world, seeks to transform the environment into a calm and peaceful place for humans, enabling them to reach the pinnacle of their spiritual and mental development. There is no doubt that numerous psychological schools exist, and dozens of psychologists have offered various psychological perspectives, each striving to define the world and eliminate its flaws based on their own views and interpretations. Some of these schools include behaviorism, existentialism, humanistic psychology, personality psychology, and others. One of the prominent scholars in the field of psychology is Martin Seligman, who, over more than thirty years, has introduced a novel school through the approach of "positive psychology," offering a fresh definition of the natural world. Seligman's theory confronted the world with new movements, phenomena, and diverse concepts. Although these concepts and terms have been extensively debated and challenged since the dawn of human knowledge by Greek, Indian, and Iranian philosophers, Seligman and his colleagues succeeded in utilizing scientific methods and a precise, coherent classification to examine virtues, concepts, and forces, thereby establishing a new intellectual school.

Positive psychology, or Seligman's perspective and school of thought, primarily aims to identify the common traits among humans in order to predict and control behavior, and ultimately to discover the unique and shared characteristics of individuals. By examining and analyzing these traits, it seeks to depict an ideal human model from which others in society can learn and take significant steps toward eliminating abnormalities and extending norms. In other words, positive psychology is in pursuit of the good life and the scientific study of the functioning of the ideal human being a science that, rather than focusing on human weaknesses and disabilities, emphasizes strengths and capabilities such as courage, gratitude, hope, happiness, mental health, enjoyment, optimism, contentment, and well being. Researchers in positive psychology study three dimensions of humans: emotions, traits, and institutions or human organizations. Emotions are categorized into three spectra of positive emotions related to the past, present, and future. Traits encompass various types such as love, compassion, kindness, honesty, and integrity. Institutions and organizations focus on positive human attitudes toward society and social life. Through this classification, human strengths are organized into six groups of virtues: wisdom and knowledge, courage, humanity, justice, temperance, and transcendence referred to as universally present virtues. Each virtue comprises a number of capacities, totaling 24 capabilities overall (Hossein-Alizadeh, 2022).

An important and noteworthy point is that some of the perspectives of scholars and thinkers in the human and social sciences directly or indirectly draw from the viewpoints of ancient scientists and theorists. Among them is Seligman's positive psychology perspective, whose manifestations can be clearly observed in the views of great Persian Dari poets. This group of poets has always strived to present themselves as reformers of society and saviors of its people from falling into the pit of abnormality and misery, and in this endeavor, they have struggled day and night using poetry and literature.

Statement of the Problem

Haidari Wujudi, a sweet-speaking poet of Dari Persian literature, has sought through his rich, didactic, and wisdom-filled poetry to share the essence of his life experiences and socio-political

engagements with others. Through this effort, he aims to instill a passion for life and hope for the future in people's hearts. In his collection of poetry, Wujudi envisions a utopia where everyone is content with the outcome of events and where everything seems to be in its proper place. The ideological proximity and worldview shared by Haidari Wujudi and Martin Seligman's positive psychology theory prompted us to explore this educational literary work through the lens of Seligman's approach. Therefore, this research examines the six core "universal virtues" in Wujudi's poetry, along with the associated character strengths found within it. The central research question of this study is: Which of Martin Seligman's universal virtues does Haidari Wujudi's poetic strategy aimed at fostering hope for the future and passion for life most closely align with?

Literature Review

To date, no independent research has specifically examined the components of positive psychology in Haidari Wujudi's poetry collection. From this perspective, the present study is both original and novel. However, certain aspects of the poet's works have previously been explored by some literary scholars. The following are notable examples:

- Radpur, Fida Mohammad (2023) authored an article titled "*A Look at the Mystical Thoughts of Haidari Wujudi*", which discusses mystical themes in Wujudi's poetry.
- Radpur, Fida Mohammad (2023) also wrote a doctoral dissertation titled "*Explanation and Analysis of Mystical Words and Terminologies in the Ghazals of Haidari Wujudi.*" This research investigates the poet's life, literary contributions, linguistic features, and provides a detailed interpretation of mystical expressions in his poems.
- Mazloom, Mohammad Tareq (2020) completed a thesis titled "*A Study of the Life, Poetry, and Ideas of Haidari Wujudi.*" This six-chapter thesis explores the literary characteristics, symbols, mystical terms, and linguistic and semantic aesthetics of Wujudi's poetry.
- Shafaqat, Shafiqullah & Ibrahim, Imamuddin (2025), in an article titled "*The Ideal Human in the Poetry of Haidari Wujudi,*" examined the traits of the ideal and superior human as portrayed in Wujudi's poetry and identified the virtues attributed to such a figure.

Discussion and Analysis

Positive Psychology

The science of psychology has a broad and extensive scope, and throughout history, various schools, theories, and approaches have emerged within its framework. Each of these schools and theories possesses unique advantages and valuable criteria. Positive psychology is one of the recent approaches that has gained prominence and attracted the attention of psychology enthusiasts. The aim of this approach is to bring about a transformation in the global psychological system by focusing on the fundamental concept of success (Asefnia, 2016).

In psychology, there exist two perspectives: positive and negative. According to the positive perspective, hope for life and happiness lead to improvement, health, and stress relief. Conversely, the negative perspective holds that a patient becomes sicker and their lifespan shortens. In the first view, an individual perceives themselves as victorious, successful, valuable, wealthy, and rational. In contrast, within the second viewpoint, a person constantly sees themselves as defeated, weak, poor, and rejected, and consequently lives according to this mental framework (Golizadeh et al., 2016).

As previously mentioned, the positive psychology approach was established by Martin Seligman (1942 AD), a Western scholar born in Albany, New York. Seligman studied at Princeton University and conducted research at the University of Pennsylvania. A notable aspect of his life is that Seligman “was raised in a religious family and remained faithful to his religious beliefs throughout his life. It can be argued that the roots and origins of his theory trace back to this religious family environment, and spirituality as one of the core traits of his personality—has had a significant influence on his scientific theories. In many of his scientific analyses, religious inclinations based on the Bible (the Gospel) are clearly observable. Martin Seligman is recognized as the father of positive psychology” (Ghorbani et al, 2023).

Positive psychology can be considered a turning point in the field of psychology, as it provides a framework for explaining and clarifying the path to success for human beings. Positive psychology pays attention to work and activity, education and upbringing, insight and love, growth and development, as well as recreation and entertainment. It seeks to understand and pursue the best aspects of human experience and does not rely solely on wishful thinking or self-deception; rather, it strives to present the best scientific methods through which the complexities of human problems and behaviors can be resolved (Seligman, 2015, p. 12).

In other words, positive psychology is one of the newest and most effective branches of psychology, grounded in the science of subjective experience, individual traits, and positive schemas. Through this foundation, the quality of life is enhanced and progressively improved. Regarding the aim of this branch of psychology, Seligman states: “Understanding, comprehending, and clarifying happiness and the subjective feeling of well-being are the central themes and core insights of positive psychology” (Seligman, 2010, p. 14).

Positive thinking refers to the correct and constructive perceptions we hold in our minds, which attract positive energy into our lives. Due to its significant role, positive thinking is considered a defining feature of psychological science. It can be understood as the utilization of all positive, invigorating, and hopeful mental capacities in life to resist surrendering to negative mental constructs and the discouraging feelings arising from difficulties in interpersonal relationships and encounters with nature (Torkmani & Niroomand, 2019).

The central themes of positive psychology are happiness, hope, wisdom, and creativity. In his book *Authentic Happiness*, Seligman categorizes the core positive emotions into three groups linked to the past, present, and future (Kar, 2006, p. 32). Achieving a good, satisfying, meaningful life based on happiness, moral virtues, and constructive human capacities has always been a fundamental concern of humanity. In the absence of modern psychological science—understood in its contemporary academic sense literature has addressed many spiritual, psychological, moral, and human problems. Indeed, many poets and writers have considered their primary mission and ultimate duty to be the guidance and enlightenment of individuals, focusing on human temperament, ethics, and character, embedding valuable insights on moral virtues and human conduct within their works (Omde-Ghyasi et al, 2025).

“Positive psychology encompasses three main domains: 1. Positive emotions; 2. Positive traits; 3. Positive institutions and organizations. Positive emotions include the study of well-being, satisfaction, contentment with the past, health and happiness in the present, and hope and optimism for the future. Positive traits of individuals involve the study of strengths and virtues such as the capacity for love, compassion, creativity, self-control, and so forth. Understanding and comprehending positive institutions and organizations requires examining the capabilities and characteristics necessary for fostering and expanding a better society, including justice, responsibility, social etiquette and manners, work ethic, and patience that is, the creation of civil institutions that guide individuals toward ideal citizenship” (Ghasemi & Qarishian, 2009).

In the current era, literature and psychology share a close relationship, forming a strong bridge between the two disciplines. Given their connection, the majority of researchers critically analyze literary works and texts through psychological perspectives, to the extent that some critics and literary scholars regard attention to psychology as essential for understanding literary works. Over recent years, literary texts have been extensively examined from the viewpoints of Freud's and Jung's theories, and it is only in the past two decades that literary works have also been analyzed from the perspective of positive psychology" (Zakari, 2023).

Components and Moral Capabilities of Positive Psychology

From the perspective of psychologists, a subtle and delicate boundary exists between talent and capability, which is not easily distinguishable. Despite many similarities between these two concepts, it can be clarified that one of their clear differences is that "capabilities are moral traits, whereas talents do not possess a moral nature; they are more innate and internal qualities that can be nurtured and developed through practice, perseverance, proper training, and commitment" (Seligman, 2019, p. 175). Another point is that capabilities can be created or cultivated, but talents, due to their innate nature, cannot be generated. In today's human society, influenced by modern era components such as technological advancement, expansion of communication, the rise of scientific and technical achievements, accelerated pace of life, and the spread of intellectual conflicts and doubts anxiety, despair, and depression have become prevalent. These are caused by emerging complexities, mechanization, neglect of spirituality, material and economic hardships, poverty, ignorance, and inequality, all of which afflict humanity. In such an environment, although some discomforts, failures, and unhappiness that humans commonly face are inevitable, noble words and admirable qualities such as hope, joy, sympathy, empathy, and kindness acquire special value and meaning. Recognizing these behavioral needs for the health of contemporary humans, Seligman has identified 24 moral capabilities that modern individuals can achieve through practice, perseverance, proper education, and commitment, allowing them to experience a lively, hopeful life free from anxiety and tension (Hossein-Alizadeh, 2022).

Finally, Seligman introduces the following components and capabilities within positive psychology, considering them essential for human happiness, flourishing, and well-being. The main components are: wisdom and knowledge, courage and bravery, humanity, justice, temperance and moderation, and transcendence and spirituality. Each of these six components includes specific capabilities, as outlined below:

Wisdom and Knowledge:

1. Curiosity and interest in the world;
2. Love of learning;
3. Judgment and critical thinking;
4. Creativity and ingenuity;
5. Emotional intelligence;
6. Perspective—seeing the big picture and overarching wisdom.

Courage:

1. Perseverance and diligence;
2. Honesty and integrity;
3. Endurance and patience.

Humanity:

1. Altruism and kindness;
2. Love and affection.

Justice:

1. Citizenship, fulfilling duties, teamwork, loyalty;
2. Fairness, equality, justice;

3. Leadership.

Temperance:

1. Self-control;
2. Humility;
3. Prudence and foresight.

Transcendence and Spirituality:

1. Wonder and appreciation of beauty and excellence;
2. Gratitude and thankfulness;
3. Hope, optimism, and future-mindedness;
4. Spirituality, purposefulness, belief, and faith;
5. Compassion and generosity;
6. Vitality and humor;
7. Enthusiasm, passion, and energy (Ghorbani et al, 2023).

Goals of Positive Psychology

Martin Seligman, by returning to fundamental and innate values, established a new perspective in psychology that, relying on internal and positive strengths, pursued various goals for advancing well-being, including:

- Creating meaning in life;
- Achieving sustainable happiness;
- Developing a positive social character;
- Building positive social relationships;
- Leading a productive life and nurturing talents;
- Experiencing positive feelings derived from pleasures;
- Attaining high satisfaction from personal capabilities (Hesarki, 2022).

The goals of positive psychology do not pertain to superficial or material aspects; rather, they have spiritual and valuable dimensions that lead to human well-being. Spiritual goals in life provide meaning to existence and help eliminate sorrow, grief, and depression from the hearts of members of society. Consequently, the heart is strengthened, individual capabilities become apparent, and the path toward growth and self-actualization is facilitated. “Beyond this, the aim of positive psychology is to deepen people’s understanding of happiness, fulfillment, satisfaction, renewal, commitment, temperance, and the value and meaning of human life. The shaping and measurement of positive outcomes for families are derived from Seligman’s research, who is regarded as a pioneer in the positive psychology movement” (Pirani, 2013).

Biography of Ghulam Haider Haidari Vujudi

Ghulam Haider Haidari Vujudi was one of the great poets of the Persian language. He was born in 1939 in the Panjshir province of Afghanistan and passed away in 2020 in Kabul. He received his primary education in his homeland and, in his youth, moved to Kabul. During his residence there, he undertook various missions and engaged in numerous social and literary activities. Throughout his valuable life, he made significant contributions to Dari Persian literature, leaving behind many lasting works. Some of Haidari Vujudi’s notable works include:

- *Divan-e Haidari Vujudi* (2020),
- *Love and Youth* (1970),
- *The Role of Hope* (1976),
- *With the Green Moments of Spring* (2nd edition, 2009),
- *A Year in the Orbit of Light* (2nd edition, 2000),
- *The Shadow of Knowledge* (6th edition, 2012),

- *The Green Images of Sound*,
- *The Appointment of Ghazal* (1992),
- *Exile in the Moonlight* (2nd edition, 2008),
- *Moments in Water and Fire* (2004),
- *The Organ of Love* (2008),
- *Quatrains and Couplets* (2nd edition, 2008),
- and commentaries on Allama Iqbal Lahori's *Secrets of the Self* and *Mysteries of Selflessness*.

The late Haidari Vujudi did not have formal education and was not an academic, but he possessed a high level of intellectual talent and had extensive studies in mystical and literary texts. He was thoroughly familiar with the books and writings of great literary authors. Moreover, he had an excellent style in writing and composition, leaving behind valuable works in prose (Radpour, 1402 [2023]: 47).

Haidari Vujudi's poetry is considered a precious heritage of Persian literature, rich with diverse themes and centered around various subjects. Although themes of love and mysticism are more prominent in his poems, and the passionate Sufi spirit is frequently evident and recognizable, he also addressed religious, ethical, social, political, patriotic, and other topics. The poet positioned himself as a compassionate preacher and a benevolent reformer, using poetry as a powerful tool to influence minds and souls for the betterment of people and society. Haidari Vujudi lived in an era and region where the surrounding environment experienced decades of political and social changes and upheavals, which had a significant impact on the nation and its people. Moral virtues and vices, as well as social and political problems, largely arose from revolutions and the chaos prevailing in society. War often led to the breakdown of ethical boundaries and social disorder, while power struggles disrupted the order of life, causing pain and hardships in the community. Haidari Vujudi personally witnessed and experienced all these disorders and hardships; thus, he stood as a social reformer, tirelessly striving to promote moral virtues, eradicate ethical vices, and eliminate injustice and social ailments. It has been said about him, "Haidari Vujudi was a mystic, humble, and self-sufficient man, whose passionate mysticism is widely reflected in his ghazals" (Ghavim, 2008: 106).

Positive Psychology Components in the Poetry of Haidari Wujudi

Wisdom and Knowledge

1. The Importance of Knowledge

Knowledge is considered a valuable and vital asset for humanity, and every member of society is aware of its worth. As a learned and reflective poet, Haidari Wujudi repeatedly emphasized the significance of knowledge and intellect. He described the contemporary era as one of wisdom, science, and culture an era where ignorance and primitive approaches have no place: "*Today is the day of knowledge, culture, and wisdom; The days of swords and spears have passed. Humanity, through knowledge, has conquered the moon; Praise be to God, the rebellion of the lunar era has ended.*" (Wujudi, 2020: 167)

He likened ignorance to a dragon, posing a real threat to human life, and emphasized the urgent need to combat it: "We must battle poverty and ignorance like dragons; With utmost bravery, we must struggle against this ancient cycle." (Ibid: 267)

Moreover, Wujudi urged people to respect knowledge and the arts: "If you understand the value of culture and life, Do not disgrace knowledge, virtue, and art." (Ibid: 414).

2. Curiosity

Curiosity about the world entails embracing experience and remaining flexible, especially when confronted with ideas that challenge one's assumptions. Curious individuals not only tolerate ambiguity but seek it, eagerly pursuing truth and knowledge. As (Ghorbani et al, 2023) state, healthy individuals are persistently inquisitive and never satisfied with what they already know.

Haidari Wujudi admired such curious individuals, especially the youth hungry for knowledge: "What is youth? With a courageous heart, serve the world; With the light of knowledge, illuminate like the sun; Awaken the sleeping world with cries like morning birds; Fight the demonic with the sword of wisdom." (Wujudi, 2020: 452–453).

3. Critical Thinking

Critical thinking requires deep, multi-dimensional analysis of problems and realities. Wujudi was keenly observant and thoughtful, analyzing the issues of his time: "O quantity and quality of this world! How long will you remain estranged from yourself? Everything you now witness in this world is the manifestation of the human soul." (Ibid: 114)

He encouraged open-mindedness and introspection: "In the garden, melancholy like a bud does not suit you; Bloom like a flower and join the fragrance of blossoms." (Ibid: 32).

4. Innovation and Creativity

Peterson has stated that initiative and innovation mean thinking of new ways and discovering constructive methods for doing things, which may include artistic work, but are not limited to it (Ghorbani et al., 2023).

Haidari Wujudi values and advocates for the essence of innovation and creativity: "A head without passion is not what the wine-lovers seek; in this gathering, thanks to pure wine, the decanter is of worth." (Haidari Wujudi, 2020: 31). He expresses weariness toward those lacking an innovative vision: "All the followers limp and the leader is blind; thus, it is impossible for us to reach the destination together." (Ibid: 98).

5. Emotional and Social Intelligence

Social or emotional intelligence refers to the ability to recognize and manage one's emotions as well as those of others. It encompasses understanding motivations, behaviors, and feelings both internal and external (Seligman, 2009: 220). Wujudi's poetry frequently reflects deep emotional awareness and empathy: "He closed the door to comfort for himself, But opened it wide for others." (Wujudi, 2020: 182).

He also condemned emotional harm and highlighted the moral cost of selfishness: "No one buys worldly comfort for a grain of barley, If, in exchange, a human heart must be broken." (Ibid: 83).

6. Perspective and Vision

Perspective refers to wisdom and the ability to see the bigger picture. A wise person, according to Wujudi, never loses their way when guided by reason.

He encouraged freedom of thought and visionary outlooks: "Haidari, fly freely in the world; The era of captivity and flightlessness has passed." (Ibid: 167)

He criticized narrow thinking and exalted ecstatic wisdom over limited intellect: "A narrow mind shames the love of perfection; I praise the madman's way of wisdom." (Ibid: 36).

Courage

1. Perseverance and Diligence

Seriousness in one's endeavors and possessing perseverance lead a person to the summits of success; an individual who rests upon the throne of negligence and laziness will never truly taste the joy of progress and salvation. Our poet has taken note of this point, and since he himself is a serious, diligent, and successful figure, he advises others to adopt this quality as well:

"Do not withdraw from the highway of your desired destination, nor release the hem of your longed-for goal. I asked a man of lofty vision: 'What is the meaning of life?' He replied: 'Endeavor with great suffering'" (ibid: 267).

Yet he does not stop there, but further recommends that a human being must strive and work with determination until the final breath of life: "Like a wave in pursuit of its quest, remain restless until the last breath of life" (ibid: 270).

Nevertheless, Haidari Wujudi does not approve of blind perseverance and unwise efforts, for they squander a person's time and fail to yield sound results; rather, labor and seriousness must be accompanied by wisdom: "Ignorant soaring leads to nowhere; in the realm of the heart, there exists no striving or diligence without knowledge" (ibid: 449).

2. Honesty

Honesty is another virtue that occupies an eminent position both in Seligman's perspective and within the teachings of Islam, which regards it as one of the highest moral values. Likewise, Haidari Wujudi honors this quality, considering it the most essential element in human prosperity and well-being: "If you desire your own survival, act with honesty; for in a world founded upon truth, there is no place for corruption" (ibid: 35).

In another verse, he presents the truthful as people destined for salvation, declaring: "If you learn the noble lesson of accepting truth, the truthful will deliver you from the chains of falsehood" (ibid: 57).

3. Patience and Forbearance

Patience and forbearance are praiseworthy traits through which their possessor neither suffers personally nor causes others to suffer; for one who is habituated to patience swallows the harsh words and severe reactions of others, taking them lightly. Haidari Wujudi emphasizes that a human being must remain as steadfast as a mountain, never losing composure in the face of any event: "With lofty determination, one must hold firm to will and choice before the world of gains and losses; in the face of the storm of events, one must ever remain steadfast and enduring, like the mountains of one's homeland" (ibid: 267).

Humanity

1. The Value of Human Beings

In the thought and worldview of Haidari Wujudi, humanity holds an exalted and precious position. He has always endeavored to institutionalize the principles and values of humanity in human societies, constantly emphasizing that people must never damage the noble edifice of humanity:

"The essence of my soul is love for humanity, and this springs from the qualities of Afghan identity. My knowledge and insight command me to believe that all the creatures of the world, white and black alike, are my brethren of one body" (ibid: 505).

2. Compassion and Philanthropy

Altruism and compassion are other moral values that are widely reflected in Haidari Wujudi's poetry. He is deeply enamored with human beings and profoundly in love with his fellow men. The poet's heart overflows with affection and insists that the hearts of all people must be filled with love; those devoid of this capacity are criticized: "For the progress and advancement of humankind and the world, one must act like the sun; and hearts that lack love are better torn apart" (ibid: 453).

Likewise, he condemns hypocrisy, which stands in opposition to compassion and altruism, declaring that hypocrisy yields only destruction and misery: "From the unity of humankind, the world prospers; and hypocrisy brings nothing but ruin" (ibid: 508).

3. Love and Affection

"Love and affection are among the traits that liberate human beings from narrow-mindedness and the prison of self-centeredness, enabling them to demonstrate self-sacrifice, devotion, and forgiveness toward others, and to establish sincere bonds with them. Recognizing the interdependence of people in society, and understanding that every pain and suffering experienced by individuals directly or indirectly affects the whole, greatly contributes to nurturing altruistic thinking. Accepting this principle compels individuals to regard the problems of others as their own, and to seek their resolution with genuine compassion" (Hosseinalizadeh, 2022).

This virtue is abundantly reflected in Haidari Wujudi's poetry, for in his perspective, there is no quality more delightful than love: "On the page of creation and within the lines of life, there is no word more delightful to me than love" (Haidari Wujudi, 2020: 488).

In another verse, he explicitly declares that as long as he lives, he will endure the hardships and blessings that come to him through the path of love, never abandoning its way: "I do not turn away from the command of love; as long as I live, I endure with dignity both the bitterness and sweetness of love" (ibid.: 353).

Haidari Wujudi considers life without love to be equivalent to death, while seeing the vitality and joy of life as dependent on love: "Life is beautiful, and you are the most beautiful; life is graceful, and you are the most graceful. Without love, life is nothing but death—death; life is dynamic, and you are the most dynamic" (ibid.: 432).

Justice

1. Citizenship

"By citizenship is meant possessing the qualities of social responsibility, loyalty, and teamwork. This capability enables an individual to participate in the social activities of the city and to be prepared to serve in endeavors that require collective cooperation" (Hosseinalizadeh, 2022).

Haidari Wujudi has paid serious attention to this matter, and it is reflected in many verses of his divan: "The slogan we have raised in the field of life is that manliness, protection of honor, and nationalism are our duties" (Haidari Wujudi, 2020: 37).

He invites citizens to unity, believing that this quality contributes to human progress and the flourishing of society: "Discord brings darkness and originates from ignorance; from the unity of humankind, the world becomes illuminated" (ibid: 411).

What distresses the poet is the disorder prevailing in his city. He advises his fellow citizens and countrymen to safeguard their dignity rather than complain about the men of power and wealth: "Complaining to the masters of authority is futile; in a city where no one cares for another, preserve your own honor" (ibid: 68).

2. Teamwork

"Social responsibility or teamwork means working as a member of a group for the sake of public interests. In fact, it is through social interactions and teamwork that human beings reveal their intellectual and practical maturity" (Ghorbani et al, 2023).

In Haidari Wujudi's poetry, too, there is evidence that highlights the importance of collective responsibility and teamwork: "In a country where the hand of unity is raised to safeguard the rank of freedom from annihilation, it is certain that such a nation will never witness the decline of its greatness in maintaining liberty" (Haidari Wujudi, 2020: 480).

3. Justice

"Justice, for Haidari Wujudi, is a fundamental and significant concept, and he regards the order of life as dependent upon the establishment of justice. He has always yearned for its realization across the world. To him, justice is a noble habit and a highly valuable moral virtue, and he wishes his ideal human being to be adorned with this quality. His distinguished model of justice is the second Caliph of Muslims, Sayyiduna 'Umar, renowned in history for his commitment to establishing justice" (Shafaqat & Ebrahimi, 2025).

Haidari Wujudi is profoundly thirsty for justice, considering nothing more commendable in thought than its realization: "I do not say that another prophet should arise; I wish only that a justice-bearer would appear" (Haidari Wujudi, 2020: 430).

The poet observes that justice has been trampled upon across the world and that arrogant powers devour the rights of the oppressed nations. Hence, he yearns for the establishment of justice everywhere: "Establishing peace and justice throughout the world is our bright and conscientious aspiration; the lamp of our life is illuminated by justice, and for this reason, we claim to be Muslims" (ibid: 505).

4. Fairness and Equality

In a composition written on the occasion of the birth of the Prophet of Humanity ﷺ, Haidari Wujudi enumerates the place of fairness and equality as follows: "In that era, Turks and Abyssinians mingled like milk and sugar, becoming equals and companions on the path of goodness. Justice, equity, and fair judgment prevailed throughout the world, and the maladies of ignorance were cured by his soul" (ibid: 628).

5. Leadership

Haidari Wujudi also instructs his audience on the path of becoming a leader, warning that laziness and sloth are the sole barriers to attaining this goal: "Arise and step out of the circle of idleness; a new day and a new month signal an era of action" (ibid: 89).

Moderation

1. Humility

Haidari Wujudi regards human perfection as rooted in humility and advises his admirers and audience to descend from the ugly and unattractive seat of arrogance, taking refuge instead in the

embrace of modesty: "The perfection of a wise man is humility; every cypress that is proud is a symbol of ignorance. Whoever is bound by the charm of selfishness is despised in the eyes of the discerning" (ibid: 99).

He further adds that humility must be practiced in youth, for it is in this stage of life that one is most inclined toward egotism and self-centeredness: "O dear Haidari! Be humble in your youth, for old age bends the back of every Pharaoh and renders him humble" (ibid: 537).

2. Self-Control and Behavioral Regulation

"Behavioral regulation and self-control refer to the process of exercising control over one's actions to achieve goals or to act in accordance with the norms of society. Individuals who have developed this trait are able to restrain instinctive responses such as anger or impulsive behavior and, instead, respond to situations in adaptive and premeditated ways" (Hosseinalizadeh, 2022).

This quality is reflected in Haidari Wujudi's poetry, as illustrated in the following verses: "The burning bush of tolerance softens stone; the claw of my patience has broken the neck of steel" (Haidari Wujudi, 2020: 35). Elsewhere he declares: "With the ill-intentioned soul, my battle and courage lie in the power of love, to the extent of my ability" (ibid: 120).

3. Foresight

Foresight denotes shrewdness, an active mind, and an inventive spirit. A person endowed with foresight and caution is less likely to fall into the depths of ruin or be exposed to regret. Haidari Wujudi also emphasizes this trait, expecting human beings to remain active and vigilant, always taking the path of prudence: "Blessed is the man who gives life to existence; the earth itself depends upon his resolve. The heart of such a man is a stormy and turbulent sea, and his being is like a mountain of iron" (ibid: 588).

Transcendence and Spirituality

1. Appreciation of Beauty and Virtue

"One of the capacities of the virtue of 'transcendence and spirituality' is the ability to be moved by the observation of beauty and moral or spiritual excellence (material or immaterial)" (Ghorbani et al, 2023). This quality has been given great attention in Haidari Wujudi's poetry, where the poet strongly emphasizes it: "What is youth? Youth is working with a strong heart for the benefit of people. It is illuminating the world with the light of knowledge like the sun. It is awakening the sleeping world through the lament of the heart, like the morning birds. It is abandoning selfishness and working like true men for the good of others. It is fighting with the sword of knowledge against those who wear the face of a human but carry the nature of a devil" (Haidari Wujudi, 2020: 542–543).

2. Spirituality

Spirituality is another dimension of the virtue of "transcendence and spirituality" reflected in Haidari Wujudi's poetry. For brevity, one example may suffice: "O Lord! For the sake of Ahmad the Chosen and his companions, turn our false thoughts around the axis of truth" (ibid: 30).

3. Mercy and Generosity

Mercy is granting others another chance, forgiving their mistakes, overlooking their shortcomings, refraining from harming them, and treating wrongdoers with patience. Our poet regards mercy and compassion as the most prominent and fundamental moral virtues, striving

tirelessly to instill them in society: "The servants of God are gentle and patient, embodying the quality of reforming people. In difficult positions and harsh circumstances, they remain kind and supportive of others. Wherever they hear the cry of the oppressed, they hasten there like the mercy of God" (ibid: 667).

Yet at times, the poet observes the opposite situation in his society, confronting individuals who are far from compassionate: "Where is the compassionate one who will remove the pain of others, who will hold the hand of the helpless, who with kindness will feel the pulse of the sick, and who will lift the burden of hardship from the shoulders of others?" (ibid: 643).

4. Purposefulness

Human beings must always set predetermined goals in life and strive to achieve them. Goals should be measurable and attainable; otherwise, they waste time and may remain unfulfilled. As Haidari Wujudi is a poet by profession, he seeks to ascend to the loftiest summits of poetic artistry: "Those devoted to love and poetry, by perseverance, elevate their words to the highest heights" (ibid: 38).

5. Hope and Optimism toward the Future

To be hopeful means to maintain belief in positive outcomes throughout one's life. A person with hope for a bright future experiences positive feelings and a joyful state of mind. According to the theory of emotional intelligence, hope signifies that an individual will not yield to anxiety, despair, or depression when confronted with challenges or difficult obstacles (Golizadeh et al., 2016).

Haidari Wujudi lives in a world filled with hope, and his life overflows with optimism toward the present and the future. He also stresses that the gate of hope is always open and never closed: "The gate of hope never closes upon anyone; convey this message from us to those who remain hopeful" (Haidari Wujudi, 2020: 37).

He further depicts life as a garden of hope: "Life is a garden of hope and desire; life is a dream, and you are the most dreamlike" (ibid: 432). In another verse, he describes hope as a means of salvation from the body, which is constantly ensnared by humiliation and disgrace: "From the pit of the body, which is the source of human degradation, the light of hope and the hand of God rescue me" (ibid: 42).

6. Emotion

Haidari Wujudi seeks to mend and construct hearts, emphasizing that individuals must not engage in wrongful acts that shatter the hearts of others: "If you wish the affairs of the world to be made right by truth, then do not vainly strive to shatter the glass of people's hearts" (ibid: 413). He identifies malice and envy as afflictions that harm both the bearer and others. The poet describes himself as free of rancor and distances himself from it: "Morning and evening, my heart's sky is free of malice; do you know whose manifestations are like the sun and the moon? Tell me" (ibid: 450).

7. Loyalty

Loyalty is one of the most important and effective moral virtues, which human beings must practice toward their fellow men. Haidari Wujudi considers loyalty the very condition of friendship: "Companions of sincerity are mirrors to one another; in the sea of loyalty, they are

like waves and pearls. At the summit of love and self-awareness, they are selfless yet conscious of the self" (ibid: 566).

Conclusion

Haideri Wujudi, one of Afghanistan's contemporary poets, possesses remarkable mastery in the art of poetry. He has left behind a valuable and extensive collection of Persian verse for his admirers. The poet lived in a society that endured years of pain, suffering, war, and exile factors that left deep scars on people's minds and spirits, with destructive consequences. Haideri Wujudi, like a compassionate teacher, a skilled psychologist, and a concerned reformer, both experienced and directly observed these adversities. He also clearly realized that his compatriots carried immense pain in their hearts, which continuously afflicted them and disrupted the order of their lives. Therefore, Haideri Wujudi sought to introduce remedies for these sufferings to the people.

Psychological perspectives, especially those aligned with theories of positive psychology, hold a prominent place in his poetry. It appears that before presenting his experiences as a poet, Haideri Wujudi conveyed his psychological insights. The recognition of positive psychology components within his verses strongly affirms this claim. In numerous poems, he engages with the virtues and capacities outlined in Martin Seligman's theory of positive psychology and presents them to his audience.

The six core virtues of Seligman's framework wisdom, courage, humanity, justice, temperance, and transcendence are evident throughout Haideri Wujudi's poetic works. Within his verses, the first virtue (wisdom) encompasses qualities such as the value of knowledge, curiosity, critical thinking, creativity, social intelligence, and perspective; the second virtue (courage) includes perseverance, sincerity, endurance, and patience; the third virtue (humanity) manifests in human dignity, compassion, altruism, love, and kindness; the fourth virtue (justice) reflects citizenship, teamwork, fairness, equity, and leadership; the fifth virtue (temperance) is expressed through humility, self-control, and prudence; and the sixth virtue (transcendence) is represented in appreciation of beauty and excellence, spirituality, mercy and generosity, purposefulness, hope and optimism for the future, passion, and loyalty. Through his poetry, Haideri Wujudi has articulated these virtues to his readers and audience with remarkable depth and clarity.

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